

Data Management Plan for Ghana

Jacklyn Armah-Hammond and Kofi Ansong-Dwamena

[Introduction](#)

[Stakeholders](#)

[Governance](#)

[Software Policy](#)

[Data Policy](#)

[Standards Policy](#)

[Actors](#)

[Functional Requirements](#)

[Business Rules / Non-Functional Requirements](#)

[Data Requirements](#)

[Database Design](#)

[System Architecture](#)

[UI/UX](#)

[QA, Testing and Review](#)

[Personnel, Roles & Responsibilities](#)

[Monitoring and Evaluation](#)

[Maintenance and Support Strategy](#)

[Capacity Building and Training](#)

[Budget](#)

[Work Breakdown Structure](#)

Introduction

This Data Management Plan (DMP) recognizes data as a vital resource for evidence-based decision-making, policy formulation, and socioeconomic development and is intended to manage and utilise data efficiently. Ghana hopes to use the plan to improve stakeholder engagement across several sectors, maintain data integrity, boost data security, and streamline data management procedures.

Data governance, data quality assurance, data infrastructure, data dissemination, and data preservation are all covered by the plan. It acknowledges the necessity of standard operating procedures for effective and dependable data-driven decision-making. The plan also emphasises the significance of data security measures to safeguard sensitive data and guarantee adherence to pertinent data protection rules.

By putting this strategy into action, the nation hopes to maximise the value of its data resources, spur innovation, and promote sustainable growth in all areas.

Stakeholders

1. Ministry of Energy
2. Energy Commission
3. Volta River Authority (VRA)
4. Ghana National Gas Company (GNGC)
5. Tema Oil Refinery (TOR)
6. Ghana National Petroleum Corporation (GNPC)
7. Petroleum Commission (PC)
8. National Petroleum Authority (NPA)
9. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)
10. Ghana Grid Company (GRIDCo)
11. Electricity Company of Ghana (ECG)
12. Enclave Power Company Ltd (EPC)
13. Northern Electricity Distribution Company (NEDCo)
14. Ghana Statistical Service (GSS)

Governance

1. Executive Steering Committee
2. Project Manager
3. Project Team
4. Technical Working Groups
5. User Advisory Groups

Software Policy

Guidelines for evaluating, adopting, and maintaining open source software components should be defined in order to successfully integrate them into the data infrastructure. At the same time, correct documentation and adherence to open source licences should be ensured. Proprietary software should be purchased and used in line with licensing requirements, including obtaining valid licences and adhering to licensing restrictions, to ensure compliant usage. Procedures for evaluating, acquiring, and administering proprietary software licences should also be specified. Frequent monitoring and audits of software licences should also be carried out, to maintain compliance and rectify any potential licensing issues or anomalies. Tools and procedures should be in place to monitor licence usage, spot unauthorised software, and swiftly address any instances of non-compliance.

Data Policy

The data policy involves a comprehensive approach to obtain information for a data infrastructure and likewise disseminate information from the data infrastructure. Spatial data should be sourced from various governmental and non-governmental entities to create a comprehensive and diverse dataset. Data could be obtained from national surveys, and administrative records and statistical databases of governmental and non-governmental institutions. Additionally, data may also be sourced from private organisations, academic institutions, and international collaborations to enrich the dataset.

Data from the data infrastructure should be disseminated to ensure accessibility and usability for various stakeholders. Interactive data visualisations, dashboards, and mapping tools should be employed to enable users to explore and analyse the data effectively. To protect sensitive information, the dissemination process should provide appropriate access controls and implement data anonymization techniques.

Standards Policy

1. Metadata Standards: The data should be well-documented and described consistently and comprehensively, providing crucial information about the data's source, quality, and usage.
2. Establishing data quality standards will help to guarantee that spatial data satisfies a number of requirements for reliability, consistency, precision, and completeness. When collecting, storing, and disseminating data, protocols should be established for data validation, error repair, and quality assurance.

Actors

1. System Administrators
2. Database Administrators
3. Database Managers
4. End Users
5. Editors

Functional Requirements

User Story reference	Expectation	Acceptance criteria
1	<p>As a System Administrator, I want to manage the installation and configuration of the operating system.</p> <p>So that I can ensure the efficient performance, availability, and robustness of the database system.</p>	<p>Given that <some pre-condition>, When <condition for action> Then <action></p>
2	<p>As a Database Administrator, I want to oversee the performance optimization of the data infrastructure.</p> <p>So that I ensure integrity, security, and effective performance of the database.</p>	<p>Given that spatial and statistical forecast data are available in the database, When I choose to view a forecast for the whole country or a province, The system presents the maps, charts and tables that were predefined for a forecast view</p>
3	<p>As a Database Manager, I want to set-up policies and standards for data management.</p> <p>So that I can support the organisation's operations, improve productivity, and drive strategic initiatives through effective database management.</p>	
4	<p>As an end user, I want to access and utilise the information stored within the database system.</p> <p>So that I can analyse data and generate reports.</p>	<p>Given that I have created the account, I expect the database to be reliable and available when I need to access it</p>

5	<p>As an editor,</p> <p>I want to contribute to the data quality with the data infrastructure.</p> <p>So that I can ensure that data is accurate, up-to-date, and accessible to users.</p>	
---	--	--

Business Rules / Non-Functional Requirements

- The system should be designed to handle high user loads and ensure availability even during peak usage times
- The system should implement robust security measures to protect sensitive data, such as encryption of data at rest and in transit, access controls, and regular security audits.
- The response times for data retrieval and processing, to ensure efficient operations should be in the range of milliseconds (e.g., 100 to 500 milliseconds) to allow users to interact with the system smoothly and without noticeable delays.

Data Requirements

Dataset	Source	Link	Coverage	Format	Year	Resolution	Category / Theme	DO we have it already?
Power Plant location	Ghana Grid Company Ltd	https://www.google.com/maps	National		2021			Yes
Annual electricity Generation by Power Plants	Ghana Grid Company Ltd		National	PDF				
Household electricity demand	Energy Commission	https://geatoolkit.energy.com.gh/	National	excel	2021			Yes
Electricity transmission and distribution network	Northern Electricity Distribution Company, Electricity	Ghana - Electricity Transmission	National	shapefile	2020			Yes

	Company of Ghana	Network - Datasets - ENERGYDATA.INFO						
Electricity Access at the regional level	Energy Commission	https://www.energycom.gov.gh/newsite/index.php/planning/energy-statistics	National	pdf	2021			Yes
Share of households using various types of fuels for cooking	Ghana Statistical Service	https://www2.statghana.gov.gh/nda/index.php/catalog	National	pdf	2021			Yes

Database Design

System Architecture

- The data infrastructure should have strong storage and management systems capable of storing and securing data assets.
- The data infrastructure should have advanced and user-friendly data processing and analytics capabilities enabling insights and evidence-based decision-making.
- The architecture incorporates data governance practices, standardised APIs for data access, visualisation tools, and robust security measures to protect the infrastructure.
- The system architecture should be scalable, resilient and interoperable to allow for seamless data exchange and accommodating the evolving data needs and emerging technologies.

UI/UX

- The interface should provide clear navigation to allow users to easily find and access different data sets, tools, and functionalities within the infrastructure.
- Effective data visualisation techniques should be implemented to present data in a visually appealing manner such as maps.

- Users should be provided with the ability to personalise their dashboards and views based on their specific data requirements and preferences.
- A robust search and filtering functionalities should be implemented to enable users to easily find specific data sets, files, or information within the infrastructure.
- The UI/UX design should be responsive and adaptable to different screen sizes and devices, including desktops, laptops, tablets, and mobile devices.
- Contextual help and documentation should be provided within the interface to assist users in understanding the functionalities, features, and workflows of the data infrastructure.

QA, Testing and Review

- Perform data validation checks and implement data quality metrics to ensure accurate and reliable data.
 - Regular audits and reviews should be conducted to assess data compliance with defined standards and identify areas for improvement.
 - Perform regular rigorous testing of the infrastructure to help identify and address any issues, bugs, or performance bottlenecks.
 - Regular reviews and audits of the infrastructure should be performed to assess the infrastructure's performance, security, and compliance with policies and regulations.
- Roles, personnel and qualifications

Personnel, Roles & Responsibilities

Personnel	Role	Responsibility
1. System Administrators	Management and upkeep of all hardware, software, and network components that make up the SDI infrastructure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Install, configure, and maintain the operating systems, web servers, database servers, and other infrastructure components. • Monitor system performance, troubleshoot issues, and ensure high availability of the SDI services.

2. Database Administrators (DBAs)	The management and administration of the database, assuring the accuracy, safety, and efficiency of the data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design and implement the database structure and data models. • Configure and improve database speed, taking into account data segmentation, query optimization, and indexing.
3. Database Managers	Overall management and governance of the project databases, ensuring data quality, consistency, and compliance with standards.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish and uphold standards, guidelines, and policies for data management. • Implement data validation and cleansing processes after defining the requirements for data quality.
4. Editors	Responsible for data creation, editing, and maintenance within the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To guarantee quality, completeness, and adherence to data standards, create and amend geospatial data. • Before submitting the data, validate and check its quality. • Keep track of the metadata for the altered data.
5. Executive Steering Committee	Responsible for making technical decisions and offering direction on the creation and deployment of project components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining technical requirements for interoperability, specifications, and standards. • Picking the best technology, tools, and data formats after evaluation.
6. Project Manager	Responsible for managing the day-to-day operations of the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitating stakeholder engagement and communication on the project. • Coordinating and monitoring project activities, schedules, and resources.
7. User Advisory Groups	Provides feedback, requirements, and recommendations to the governance bodies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing feedback on consumer needs, preferences, and demands. • Recognizing and expressing user issues, issues, and opportunities. • Taking part in user acceptability testing and offering comments on system performance.

Monitoring and Evaluation

- Clear objectives and key performance indicators (KPIs) that align to the data infrastructure should be established.
- Robust data collection mechanisms should be implemented to gather real-time data on metrics like data quality, timeliness and availability.
- Stakeholders from various sectors of the country have to be engaged to gather feedback on user experiences and challenges.
- Regular performance evaluation should be conducted to assess whether the data infrastructure meets its defined objectives and KPIs and identify areas for improvement.

Maintenance and Support Strategy

- Effective support channels should be established to promptly address user queries and technical issues.
- Proactive monitoring should be implemented to enable real-time system health checks and timely issue resolution.
- Preventive measures like data backups and capacity planning should be implemented to minimise disruptions and maintain data integrity, while regular updates, patches, and hardware upgrades should be made to address security vulnerabilities and improve performance.

Capacity Building and Training

- Capacity building and training for data infrastructure personnel are vital for ensuring effective management and utilisation of the infrastructure.
- Personnel should be provided with the necessary knowledge and skills to enhance their ability to handle data governance, management, security and infrastructure maintenance and keep them abreast with industry trends and best practices.
- Capacity building and training of personnel will enable them to optimise system performance and leverage the full potential of the data infrastructure, leading to improved data-driven decision-making.

Budget

Funding could be obtained from

- Government Funding sources
- Public-Private Partnerships
- International Funding and Aid

- User Fees and Subscriptions

The breakdown of the estimated cost of development of a data infrastructure is as follows:

- Infrastructure cost including cost of hardware (servers, storage devices, etc.), software, network infrastructure (routers, switches, cables, etc.): \$200,000
- Data Collection and Acquisition cost: \$50,000
- System Development and Maintenance cost: \$300,000
- Cost of implementation of data security measures including cybersecurity measures: \$100,000
- Capacity building and training of personnel: \$100,000

Work Breakdown Structure

1. Planning and Requirements Gathering: Goals, objectives and scope of the spatial data infrastructure should be defined and key stakeholders identified.
2. Data Inventory and Assessment: Spatial data sources within the country should be identified and their data assessed for quality, accuracy and completeness.
3. Data Standards and Metadata: Data and metadata standards should be established to ensure consistency of spatial data.
4. Data Acquisition and Integration: Spatial data should be acquired from various sources including surveys, remote sensing and other data providers.
5. Spatial Data Storage and Management: Design and implement a spatial data repository and implement data backups and disaster recovery.
6. Spatial Data Services: Implement spatial data services, such as web mapping services (WMS) and web feature services (WFS). Interfaces for spatial data integration with external systems or applications.
7. Spatial Data Analysis and Visualization: Interactive maps, visualisation dashboards and reporting mechanisms should be developed.
8. Capacity Building and Training: Programs should be designed to build the capacity of stakeholders.
9. Monitoring and Continuous Improvement: Monitor the performance and usage of the data infrastructure and collect user feedback.